

DIGITAL TRANSITION, DIGITAL INNOVATION HUBS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT – AN EU CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Purpose – The study maps EU-wide Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and assesses the contribution of digitalisation to member states' economic development.

Methodology/approach - To provide an overview of EU DIHs, we analysed data from the European Commission's Smart Specialisation Platform (S3P). An econometric analysis was based on cross-sectional data and regression models. To assess the extent to which digitalisation produces economic and social effects, we opted for an aggregate indicator of macroeconomic outcomes with independent variables from the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI).

Findings – More than half of the change in GDP per capita is explained by the change in the analysed variables: electronic information sharing, social media, e-commerce and selling online cross-border, driven by digitally transitioned EU SMEs.

Research limitations/implications – Empirical research was conducted on EU member states and in the Covid-19 pandemic period of 2019-2021. Future research could consider relative country size and relative economic power as additional variables.

Practical implications – By leveraging the results of the study, decision makers can better understand the benefits of supporting SMEs in the adoption of digital solutions and leveraging DIHs impact.

Originality/value – Research results provide valuable contributions towards the improvement of SME performance in EU.

Key words: digital transformation, SME, digital innovation hubs.

Introduction

Recent studies (e.g., Borowiecki et al., 2021) have signalled an increase of the global digital economy, which is considered to be an important pillar for economic growth of individual nations. Globally it is estimated that by 2025, the digital economy will account for over 15% of the national gross domestic product (GDP) (World Bank, 2022).

The “Digital Europe Programme” aims to strengthen the international competitiveness of member states and, implicitly, of the European Union (European Commission, 2022a). The digital transition of EU nations has been embedded in concerns about the resilience of member states' economies, which have been impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic crisis (Georgescu et al., 2022). An important role is given to DIHs (Georgescu et al., 2021), which were created to facilitate access to innovative digital solutions for all economic and social actors.

The strong impact of digitalisation (especially in the last decade) had the effect of changing perceptions of value creation and the use of technology (Peter et al., 2020; Sassanelli et al., 2021). Studies have shown that digitalisation is changing the profile, needs and behaviour of consumers (Teece, 2010). To maintain and improve their competitiveness, organisations need to adopt business models that allow them to adapt to consumer needs, increase opportunities for innovation, increase productivity, reduce costs, and develop sustainably (Kraft et al., 2022).

For a digital transition, DIHs and the assessment of the contribution of digitalisation to economic development are concepts that have not yet been researched to a great extent. This study fills a research gap by addressing two interrelated research issues: a) the extent to which DIHs have been established (and planned) to support the digital transition (in the Covid-19 pandemic and post-pandemic periods); and b) the extent to which digital innovation has contributed to EU member states' economic growth. In order to answer the identified research problems, we mapped the establishment and development of DIHs in the period 2019-2021 and conducted an econometric analysis to assess the contribution of digitalisation to economic development.

Literature Review

Digital transformation is defined as the strategic change associated with the application of digital technologies to businesses and governments, based on new consumer needs and market changes (Peter et al., 2020; Prince, 2018). Digital transformation is an ongoing process that forces and supports all actors in an economy, including small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), large corporations but also associative and non-associative business structures to reflect paradigms and improve business models according to new market requirements (Georgescu et al., 2022).

The increase of digital performance in the EU economy resulted to some degree in the improvement of productivity and increasing importance of collaborative networks (Baranauskas & Raišienė, 2022; Jurčević et al., 2020). Also, it is assumed that the accelerated digitalisation of the economy in the last two years following the Covid-19 outbreak was an important argument for the transition from traditional business models to business models with integrated digital platforms. However, several challenges emerge associated with the ongoing digitalisation, including sustainable management (e.g., vulnerabilities in collaborative networks and an increased asymmetry of information on digital resources).

In 2021, there were approximately 22.6 million SMEs registered in the European Union, representing 99% of all businesses in the EU (European Commission, 2022b). DIHs play an important role in facilitating the digital transition, focusing on providing support to SMEs, considered to be important actors in the EU economy (Georgescu et al., 2021). According to the results of previous studies, SMEs are constantly concerned with boosting productivity and increasing competitiveness (Viswanathana & Telukdari, 2021). Compared to traditional SMEs, digitally connected ones can generate more value, especially from international transactions (WTO, 2019). Also, SMEs with a lower level of digital maturity are more interested in applying collaborative projects, precisely to enhance the benefits of innovation and for faster digitalisation (Volpe et al., 2021). Hence, with ongoing digital transformation and digitalisation, and new challenges emerging, DIHs might contribute to economic growth at levels underestimated by stakeholders.

Methodology

To assess the extent to which DIHs were established to support the digital transition, we conducted an analysis based on data available on the S3P (European Commission, 2022c). The 27 EU member states maintain a total of 625 registered DIHs, an average of 23 DIHs per EU member state. There are major differences between member states, primarily driven by country and economic size (Table 1).

For example, Spain is the country with the highest number of registered DIHs (90), while Malta has the lowest number of DIHs (2). Of the total DIHs (Figure 1), only 60% are fully operational, 31% are in preparation, and 9% are potential DIHs from the EU H2020 project. Periodically, the EU launches funding calls and selects new DIHs to be part of the EU DIH network. There were 316 candidate DIHs reported on the Smart Specialisation Platform (S3P). Comparing the total number of registered DIHs at the EU level with the number of candidate DIHs, it is observed that the member states (Italy, Spain, Germany, and France) with the most registered DIHs also have the most candidate DIHs.

As collaborative structures based on the idea of collaboration platforms, DIHs were created to provide support in the digital transition of European SMEs. Therefore, we have chosen to conduct an econometric analysis based on a) the dependent variable of real GDP per capita (GDPc) as a measure of the intensity of economic activity (data was collected from the EUROSTAT databases) (European Commission, 2022b); and b) independent variables (according to the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) (European Commission, 2022d), namely Electronic information sharing (% enterprises) (Eis); Social media (% enterprises) (Sm); Big data (% enterprises) (Bd); Cloud (% enterprises) (C); e-Invoices

(% enterprises) (eI); SMEs selling online (% SMEs) (So); e-Commerce turnover (% SME turnover) (eCt); and Selling online cross-border (% SMEs) (Soc).

Table 1. Metrics of EU DIHs

	DIHs				DIH in H2020 Projects		Candidate DIHs
	Total	FO	IP	PDH	FO	IP	
Mean	23,1	13,9	7,1	2,1	2,9	0,9	11,7
Minimum	2	0	1	0	0	0	0
Maximum	90	66	25	8	17	4	45
Sum	625	375	192	58	78	25	316
Count	27	27	27	27	27	27	27

Notes: Total = Total number of DIH; FO – Fully Operational; IP – In Preparation; PDH - Potential from H2020 (based on data from European Commission, 2022c).

Figure 1. DIHs by Nation and Type (based on data from European Commission, 2022b)

Based on the literature, our hypothesis was that an increase of the degree of digitalisation in the economies of the EU member states has beneficial influences on macroeconomic outcomes. The analysis period was limited to three years (2019 to 2021), precisely to capture the influences of the pandemic period in which SMEs were forced to use digital technology to overcome specific challenges. In order to assess the relationship between the degree of digitalisation and the dynamics of EU member states' economies, correlation and regression analyses were performed. The data analysis package from Microsoft Excel was used for data processing.

Results

The first step of the econometric analysis was to summarise in a synthetic and explicit form the database and to test the representativeness of the data set. The descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2.

For the analysed variables, the standard deviation indicates a degree of data scattering below the mean values at the sample level. The Kurtosis index is in the range (-1; 3), which indicates that the sample values are close to average (predominantly lower than average). The Skewness index has values close to zero which indicates a symmetrical distribution to the left (in the case of Eis), and to the right (in the case of the other variables). From the average point of view, minimum and maximum values, the data offers the following interpretation:

Table 2. Descriptive statistics- EU SME Performance 2019-2021 based on GDP and DESI Factors

	<i>Eis</i>	<i>Sm</i>	<i>Bd</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>el</i>	<i>So</i>	<i>eCt</i>	<i>Soc</i>	<i>GDPc</i>
Mean	35,17	23,86	12,90	22,81	26,31	18,22	11,49	8,95	27508,89
Standard Deviation	9,36	9,99	6,13	13,88	18,98	7,52	5,11	3,63	17771,64
Kurtosis	-0,48	-0,70	-0,08	0,27	2,81	-0,42	2,10	-0,17	2,45
Skewness	-0,03	0,50	0,84	1,06	1,77	0,62	0,95	0,51	1,53
Minimum	14,00	8,00	5,00	6,00	7,00	6,00	2,00	2,00	6380,00
Maximum	54,00	44,00	31,00	62,00	95,00	38,00	29,00	18,00	86550,00
Count	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81	81

- On average, 35.17% of EU SMEs, during the Covid-19 pandemic period, were able to continue their activity using electronic information sharing platforms (EIS). The minimum value of this indicator was recorded by Hungary (throughout the analysed period), and the maximum value was recorded in Belgium (in 2019).
- On average, 23.86% of SMEs are active on social media (Sm). Finland is the country where SMEs make the most use of social networks (44%). At the opposite side is Romania, where only 8% of SMEs are active on social media platforms.
- Only 12.90% of SMEs manage and capitalise on large and complex data sets (Bd) (which require appropriate software). The exploitation of these data sets is more intense in Malta (where 31% of companies have software and process large data sets). The lowest utilisation rates were identified in Romania and Cyprus (5%).
- On average, 22.81% of EU SMEs use Cloud (C) for data storage and processing. Cloud services are highly valued in Finland (62% of businesses store data in the Cloud), but only 6% of Bulgarian SMEs use Cloud platforms and services.
- On average, 26.31% of SMEs issue electronic invoices (el). In Italy, 95% of businesses use electronic invoices. At the opposite pole is Latvia, where only 7 out of 100 SMEs issue electronic invoices.
- At EU level, only 18.22% of SMEs have online sales (So). Most companies that have online sales are in Denmark (38%). At the opposite side is Bulgaria, which at least recorded modest increases (from 6% in 2019 to 8% in 2021).
- On average, at EU level, 11.49% of total sales in SMEs are made on e-commerce platforms (eCt). Ireland is the country with the largest share of e-commerce in total sales (29%). In Bulgaria, less than 3% of total sales are made through e-commerce.
- On average, only 8.95% of EU SMEs make cross-border online sales (Soc). Ireland is leading in this respect (18%). At the opposite side is Romania, where only two out of 100 companies make cross-border online sales.
- Real GDP per capita (GDPc) records average values of 27,509 euros (at sample and period level). The minimum value of the indicator was recorded in Bulgaria (6,380 euros in 2020) and the maximum value was recorded in Luxembourg (86,550 euros in 2021).

The correlation analysis at the level of the variables in the sample was the second step of the econometric analysis. The results (shown in Table 3) indicate that there is a positive correlation (over 0.75) between two independent variables (So and eCt).

In order to eliminate the risks related to the correlated data, we ran two regression models that would capitalise on the information provided by the two variables, but in different regression equations. The first equation excludes eCt, and the second excludes So (see Table 4). The statistical confidence assumed for the regression analysis was 95%, and the assumed significance threshold was 0.05. For both equations, the significance presents values lower than the assumed significance threshold, the models being considered statistically valid. Adjusted R Square is 55% in the first model and 58% in the second model, which indicates that more than half of the GDP per capita change is justified by the variation of the variables included in the analysis.

Table 3. Correlation Analysis

	<i>Eis</i>	<i>Sm</i>	<i>Bd</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>el</i>	<i>So</i>	<i>eCt</i>	<i>Soc</i>	<i>GDPc</i>
<i>Eis</i>	1								
<i>Sm</i>	0,47	1							
<i>Bd</i>	0,45	0,60	1						
<i>C</i>	0,38	0,67	0,62	1					
<i>el</i>	0,26	0,29	0,20	0,63	1				
<i>So</i>	0,36	0,55	0,45	0,64	0,27	1			
<i>eCt</i>	0,23	0,41	0,39	0,52	0,20	0,79	1		
<i>Soc</i>	0,38	0,54	0,34	0,39	0,05	0,70	0,67	1	
<i>GDPc</i>	0,53	0,70	0,56	0,56	0,28	0,45	0,53	0,52	1

Table 4. Regression Analysis

First equation	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	8,57	0,19	44,96	0,00	8,19	8,95
<i>Eis</i>	0,01	0,01	1,98	0,05	0,00	0,02
<i>Sm</i>	0,02	0,01	3,16	0,00	0,01	0,04
<i>Bd</i>	0,02	0,01	1,58	0,12	0,00	0,04
<i>C</i>	0,00	0,01	0,58	0,56	-0,01	0,02
<i>el</i>	0,00	0,00	0,63	0,53	0,00	0,01
<i>So</i>	-0,01	0,01	-1,38	0,17	-0,03	0,01
<i>Soc</i>	0,05	0,02	2,40	0,02	0,01	0,08
R Square = 0,59		Adjusted R Square =0,55		Significance F =5,39x10 ¹²		
Second equation	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	8,396	0,19	44,71	0,00	8,02	8,77
<i>Eis</i>	0,01	0,01	2,36	0,02	0,00	0,02
<i>Sm</i>	0,03	0,01	3,85	0,00	0,01	0,04
<i>Bd</i>	0,01	0,01	1,31	0,20	-0,01	0,03
<i>C</i>	-0,01	0,01	-0,76	0,45	-0,02	0,01
<i>el</i>	0,00	0,00	0,81	0,42	0,00	0,01
<i>Soc</i>	0,00	0,02	0,00	1,00	-0,04	0,04
<i>eCt</i>	0,03	0,01	2,67	0,01	0,01	0,06
R Square = 0,6172		Adjusted R Square = 0,58		Significance F =5,06x10 ¹³		

The regression analysis also indicates that four variables (*Eis*, *Sm*, *Soc* and *eCt*) have a statistically positive and significant influence on GDP per capita; in other words, a one percent increase in SMEs that use electronic data sharing, those that are active on social media and those that have cross-border sales have the positive effect of increasing a nation's GDP per capita; rather, as the share of online sales in total turnover increases, the prospects for GDP growth per capita increase; and finally, the free term is statistically significant, which indicates that there are (of course) other variables influencing GDP per capita.

Discussion and Conclusion

At the EU economic level, the predominant economic agents in terms of units are SMEs. Against the background of the Covid-19 pandemic, there has been a growing concern of national and European authorities to support SMEs in support of their digital transition. In this context, an important role is assigned to DIHs, which provide products and services tailored to the business community they support. Studies have shown that digitalisation and innovation support SMEs in overcoming crisis-induced barriers (economic, financial, pandemic), increasing the resilience and sustainability of economies.

This study assesses the extent to which businesses have leveraged the results of digital innovation during the Covid-19 pandemic crisis. The results of the study show that, at the EU level, the degree of involvement of SMEs in electronic data sharing and social media has increased. At the same time, the SMEs' interest for the use of big data, cloud platforms and electronic invoicing has increased. More dominant is the increase in online sales (domestic and cross-border) as well as the increase in the share of e-sales revenue in total sales revenue. These transformations have had an impact on the macroeconomic outcomes at EU level. Econometric research has shown that one percent increase in businesses that (a) share information electronically, (b) are active on social media/have digital marketing activity, and (c) have cross-border sales, contribute to an increase in GDP per capita as follows: (a) 0.01; (b) 0.02-0.03; (c) 0.05. As the share of online sales in total sales increases, GDP per capita increases by 0.03.

Our results are convergent with other results of previous studies. For example, Kovács et al. (2022) investigated whether the DESI variables contribute to increasing convergence at EU member state level. Using real GDP per capita as a criteria for grouping EU countries, the authors identified a so-called "Matthew effect" (e.g., Perc, 2014), that describes the "rich get richer" phenomenon. In other words, the authors confirmed the contribution of DESI variables to the increase of convergence and implicitly to the increase of GDP per capita, but with more consistent effects at the level of the developed countries. This effect is also confirmed by our analyses which showed that the developed EU countries (such as Spain, Italy, Germany, France, and the Netherlands), that have the most fully operational DIHs, also have the most DIHs candidates to be recognised at EU level. Therefore, the contribution of DIHs to ensuring the digital transition of SMEs in these countries will be more consistent, and the effects on GDP per capita is assumed to be more obvious.

Other studies have shown that the attention of decision makers on the digital economy has increased. Liu (2022) reviewed data provided by DESI and showed that the best performing economies in the EU are strongly correlated with at least one of the DESI indicators. Other studies that support the contribution of digitalisation to increasing macroeconomic outcomes have been conducted by Grigorescu et al. (2021), Jurcevic et al. (2020), and Stanley et al. (2018), who all analysed the impact of digital transformations on economic and social outcomes.

However, we acknowledge that our research is limited to EU member states and only covers the short Covid-19 pandemic period (2019-2021). In addition, future research might acknowledge country size and economical drivers as an important factor in the analysis. Therefore, the representativeness of the results must be viewed in light of these limitations. As a consequence, we consider a cluster analysis to identify the impact of digitalisation of SMEs by categories of EU member states, grouped according to economic power (estimated by real GDP per capita). In this analysis we also consider the correlation of the intensity of DIH activity with the economic performance of member countries.

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